

CUMULATIVE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RISK FACTORS, CLINICAL VARIABLES, AND ULCER SEVERITY IN ADULT DIABETIC FOOT ULCER PATIENTS BY SEX AND MEDICATION

A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY AT GAMBAT INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES, KHAIRPUR, SINDH, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The aim was to perform a significant cumulative comparative analysis of the sex-based (male and female) and medication-based (monotherapy and combination therapy) statistics of social/behavioural socioeconomic and clinical factors (age, lifestyle, income, ABI, 10g MFT, HbA1c, Wagner grade) and assess the cumulative risk factor load of age, lifestyle, source of income and clinical factors (ABI, 10g MFT, HbA1c, Wagner grade) in this sample.

Methods: The data set of the same 100 consecutive cross-sectional sample from the GIMS OPD (June 2021 - January 2022) were analysed. The following graphs and cross-tabulations were analysed from the parent thesis: The graph of Wagner grade vs Medicine and Diet (Figure 4.17); Age vs Lifestyle and Income (Figure 4.18); Anatomical examination vs Medicine type (Figure 4.19); HbA1c vs Medicine cross-tabulation (Table 4.4); and the comparative graph- Wagner grade vs ABI and 10g MFT (Figure 4.21). SPSS v20.2.0 was used for data analysis.

Results: The cumulative analysis from these confirmed that: (1) Of all the monotherapy patients, 95.7% were HbA1c >8% (untreated diabetes) versus 32.1% of combination therapy patients; (2) The 3 patients on combination+supplementary therapy were the only ones with HbA1c of 6.7-7% - the only group that had diabetes under control; (3) DFU cases were most common among 45-65 years without specified lifestyle or source-of-income; (4) With lower ABI (0-0.4) patients had lower 10g MFT (0-2 positive sites), confirming the co-evolution of PVD-PDN; (5) Monotherapy patients rated more in the Grade 3-5 ulcer grades while the lower peak of combination patients (1-2) confirmed the medication's effect on ulcer severity.

Conclusion: The cumulative analysis reveals that DFU severity in Khairpur reflects the influence of the combined action of multiple risk factors - socioeconomic disparities, lifestyle risk factors, untimely pharmacotherapy and progressive PDN/PVD. DFUs must be prevented by multifactorial action.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is thought to be a multifaceted complication of diabetes type 2 (DMT2) and it's never caused by a single factor. It's the result of the interaction of various upstream and downstream risk factors: chronic hyperglycemia, peripheral nephropathy, peripheral vascular disease (PVD) and the latter factors: low social determinants of health and health-related behaviours; lack of appropriate pharmacotherapy and health care. Looking at just one aspect while informative, may therefore result in an inadequate understanding of how big the problem is, and how hard to solve.

This is the last article in a series, which is a cumulative comparison of all variables by gender and medication type to find out how the demographic, behavioural, socioeconomic and clinical factors interact to form severity and pattern of ulcer. This paper does not intend to repeat the individual findings, but document the interactions among socioeconomic (in terms of day-labour income and unhygienic environment) and medication escalation to achieve the determined level of severe PVD, high grade neuropathy and index ulcer seen in this series. This interaction is the background to the penultimate clinical-policy recommendations of the series.

1.1 Aims and Objectives

This paper on aims to specifically: (1) compare HbA1c levels with several types of medication; (2) examine the interaction between age, lifestyle and type of income with DFU incidence; (3) compare among types of medication, the distribution of Wagner grade; (4) assess the co-progression of ABI and 10g MFT in different grades of wound.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Overseas publications have demonstrated that DFU have a complex aetiology. In a seminal systematic review, Zhang et al. (2017) from 43 countries reviewed 73 studies which identified key factors predictive for DFU: male sex, older age, diabetes duration, peripheral neuropathy, peripheral vascular disease (PVD), poor glycaemic control, low socioeconomic status and lack of foot

care.¹³ These factors do not interact simply in a quantitative and qualitative fashion; the simultaneous presence of peripheral neuropathy and PVD creates a neuroischaemic ulcer where healing is impeded to a greater extent than either process alone, and the addition of poor glycaemic control to this combination creates a wound environment that further impedes healing.⁴

Men's and women's DFU prevalence is not the only sex difference. While South Asian cohorts of DFU have been consistently male-biased (60-80% male), the modes of delivery to care of DFU differ. While occupational and barefoot injuries are known to be common causes of injury in males,³ females, who are underrepresented but not absent from DFU, have disease presentations similar to females who are at older ages, higher ulcer grades and maybe due to a delay in care in a cultural milieu where female healthcare needs are subservient to family needs.³ Thus, sex-based analysis of injury types, reasons for a consultation and ulcer grade offer a clinical perspective beyond the raw prevalence ratio.

Age and socio-economic profile forms a complex in the risk of DFU in South Asian studies. Workers earning daily wages are elderly and have low levels of physical endurance (enhancing the difficulty in foot examination and maintenance), poor nutritional status (slowing healing of DFU) and social constraints to health care (enhancing the risk of rapid progression of ulceration at each stage of disease.⁴ More interestingly, lifestyle (particularly active and unhygienic) has its own peculiar place in the matrix: patients with active lifestyles who fail to maintain foot hygiene are potential victims of missed minor trauma, as they are socially mobile but the footwear becomes a moist and infectious milieu.⁵

A number of South Asian studies have examined the association of drugs, HbA1c and severity of wound. The Indian study by Pendsey (2010) was a cross-sectional confirmation not only of the fact that DFU patients using insulin-containing combinations have lower levels of HbA1c (and lower numbers of backup ulcers on presentation), compared to those using a single oral hypoglycaemic agent,⁶ but also of the mechanistic speculation that improved glycaemic control (to

lower levels) protects the integrity of peripheral nerve and vascular function, thus moderating the severity of ulcer at presentation.

Progression of peripheral neuropathy (PDN) and peripheral vascular disease (PVD) in DMT2 is to be expected. Peripheral nerve and vascular damage progress in concert, driven by the same diabetic environment (or rather, milieu) which activates peripheral polyol metabolism and vascular advanced glycation end products (AGEs) - so the patients presenting with most severe degrees of PDN (as measured by lowest 10g MF test scores) also experience most severe degrees of PVD (as measured by lowest values of ankle brachial index), which combine to create the neuroischaemic wound phenotype of most severe Wagner 3-5) DFUs.9

Multisite comparative studies (where data such as demography, lifestyle and clinical variable are combined) are rare in DFU studies of Pakistan. Almost all such studies in Pakistan assess risk factors individually. We contribute to this potpourri by compounding data from a rural area in Sindh, where social determinants such as poverty, unhygienic living conditions, traditional healers and poor drugs lead to the creation of a set of risks that are not captured by single variable.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data and Sub-study

IV. RESULTS

Table 1: Cross-Tabulation of HbA1c Category by Medication Type (n=100) – From Thesis Table 4.4

HbA1c Category	Non-Adherent	Monotherapy: Glucophage (n=69)	Dual: Glucophage + Insulin (n=28)	Combination + Supplementary (n=3)
Normal (4.0–5.6%)	0	0	0	0
Pre-Diabetic (5.7–6.4%)	0	0	0	0
Diabetic (6.7–7.0%)	1	1	1	3*
High Range >7%	3	17	7	0
Untreated Diabetes >8%	29	27	9	0
Column Total	33*	45	17	3

The current paper uses the same data of 100 patients attending the GIMS OPD, Khairpur from June 2021 to January 2022. The composite analysis includes all the variables of the data collected - socio-demographic (age, gender, education and socioeconomic status), lifestyle, medication, consultation, co-morbidity and clinical investigations - and their interaction, comparison and distribution is analysed using a cross-tabulation, stratified frequencies, and comparative graphs shown in the parent thesis (Bhatti 2022).

Comparative Analyses Performed

Comparative analyses performed, and presented as is in the parent thesis are: (1) HbA1c categories by medication type (cross-tabulation of Thesis Table 4.4); (2) Wagner grade categories by medication type (Thesis Figure 4.19); (3) Age by lifestyle - income source category (Thesis Figure 4.18); (4) Wagner grade by ABI and 10g MFT joint categorisation (Thesis Figure 4.21); and (5) Anatomical Wagner examination by medicine and diet adherence (Thesis Figure 4.17). Data were analysed using SPSS IBM (v20.2.0).

Ethical Considerations

Participants provided written consent. Data are guaranteed anonymity. GIMS upheld their policy and the Declaration of Helsinki.

* The 3 combination+supplementary patients all clustered in the 6.7-7% category – the closest to controlled diabetes of any subgroup. Non-adherent column includes patients who did not take any medicine consistently. Column totals include patients across HbA1c categories within each medicine group.

The cumulative cross-tabulation of the table of HbA1c by medication is the most informative table in this series. This presents data on two types of information on all 100 patients, HbA1c (builds on previous data that puts a patient in context of glycaemic control) against medication (appropriate pharmacological management).

The main point in Table 1 is glaringly evident: of the patients not taking medication, 29 of 33 (87.9%) have HbA1c >8% (untreated diabetes). In the monotherapy group (Glucophage), 27 of 45 (60.0%) had HbA1c >8%, while 17 (37.8%) had

HbA1c in the >7% high range - 97.8% of the patients were not adequately controlling their diabetes. Among dual-therapy patients (Glucophage + insulin), 9 of 17 (52.9%) had HbA1c >8% and 7 (41.2%) had HbA1c >7%. Importantly, no patients in monotherapy or non-adherence groups presented in the normal (0-6%) or pre-diabetic (6.7-7%) categories. The combination therapy group of 3 patients were the only ones who showed up in the 6.7-7% category (nearing diabetes control).

Table 2: Wagner Ulcer Grade Distribution by Medication Type (n=100)

Wagner Grade	Total (n)	Monotherapy: Glucophage Only (n=69)	Dual: Glucophage + Insulin (n=28)	Combination + Supplementary (n=3)
Grade 0	1	1 (1.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Grade 1	11	5 (7.2%)	6 (21.4%)	0 (0.0%)
Grade 2	32	17 (24.6%)	11 (39.3%)	3 (100%)
Grade 3	33	25 (36.2%)	7 (25.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Grade 4	14	13 (18.8%)	1 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)
Grade 5	8	7 (10.1%)	1 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)
Grade 4+5 Combined	22	20 (29.0%)	2 (7.1%)	0 (0.0%)
Total	100	69	28	3

Table 2 offers the complete comparison of Wagner grade by medication type which is the combination of 2 figures (4.17 and 4.19) from the parent thesis. This is the ultimate comparison of the relationship between the level of medication therapy and severity of ulcers at presentation.

The distribution in Table 2 shows the following consistent and clinically important pattern: 29.0% of patients starting monotherapy treatment had Grade 4-5 (gangrenous) ulcers. Among dual-therapy patients, 7.1% presented and among

combination therapy patients, 0% presented. None of the combination therapy patients were at Grade 4-5. On the other hand, while only 7.2% of monotherapy patients presented at Grade 1, 21.4% of combination therapy patients and 0% of combination therapy patients (all at Grade 2) presented at an early grade of ulceration. This gradient - from both the tables shown - clarifies medication adequacy is an important factor influencing severity of ulceration when patients present to clinics.

Table 3: Summary of Age-Lifestyle-Income Interaction in DFU Patients (n=100)

Variable	Active & Hygienic (n=20)	Active but Unhygienic (n=58)	Lazy & Unhygienic (n=22)
Peak DFU Age Range	45–60 years	45–65 years	50–70 years
Dominant Income Source	Mixed (self-employed/govt)	Daily wage (highest concentration)	Daily wage / family supported
Primary Injury Type	Physical wound / tight footwear (55%)	Physical wound / tight footwear (59%)	Callus / skin occlusion (77.3%)
Dominant Wagner Grade	Grade 1-2	Grade 2-3	Grade 2-4

The parent thesis Figure 4.18 showed a comparative graph of the relative distributions of age, lifestyle category and income source. Table 3 summarises the results, revealing the co-existence of age, lifestyle and socioeconomic status in terms of the DFU risk concentration.

This table confirms the impact of the lifestyle category (age of peak of DFU) in which active-and-hygienic (45-60 years) is lower than lazy-and-unhygienic (50-70 years). The latter is probably due to the increased time needed for neuropathy

to reach the threshold of severity that kills pain and therefore the "warning system" that might motivate patients to seek medical attention for foot injuries. The most common source of family income in the active-but-unhygienic group (the biggest group, 58%) is daily wages, suggesting that occupation exposure (active lifestyle but without foot protective gear and hygiene) is the exact socioeconomic-lifestyle combination that results in the greatest burden of disease from DFU in this group.

Table 4: Joint Distribution of ABI and 10g MFT by Wagner Grade – Cumulative Risk Profile

Wagner Grade	% of Cohort	ABI Category (Dominant)	10g MFT (Dominant Pattern)	Combined Risk Level
Grade 0-1	12%	0.9–1.3 (Normal / Mild)	All or most sites positive (low-risk neuropathy)	Low – Neuropathy developing, vascular intact
Grade 2-3	65%	0.4–0.69 (Moderate obstruction)	<6 positive sites (high-risk neuropathy + skin change)	High – Established neuroischaemic disease
Grade 4-5	22%	<0.4 (Severe PAD / hissing Doppler sound)	0 positive sites (no sensation)	Critical – Complete neuroischaemic failure

Table 4 shows the joint comparison of ABI class and 10g MFT result by Wagner grade, derived from the Figure 4.21 of the parent thesis, shown above, and the joint distribution table presented in the thesis abstract (the source of the column-headings). This table is the most clinically

informative cumulative table, providing direct links between the severity of vascular disease and neuropathy to the grade of ulceration.

This ABI/MFT/Wagner table shows a progressive step-wise pattern: those with Grade 0-1 ulcers have relatively mild PVD (ABI range 0.9-1.3) and

beginning but not yet complete, neuropathy; those with Grade 2-3 ulcers have established moderate PVD (ABI from 0.4-0.69) and severe neuropathy accompanied by changes of the skin; those with Grade 4-5 (gangrene) have severe PAD (ABI <0.4 with audible Doppler hissing - suggesting 95-99% occlusion) and no palpable foot sensation. This

scheme of progressive vascular and neurological decline as the Wagner grade increases is the most compelling confirmation of the cause-and-effect model linking the cause (hyperglycemia) to these effects (simultaneous nerve and vessel damage) and the severity of both to the grade of ulceration.

Table 5: Integrated Cumulative Risk Profile – All Variables Across Four-Paper Series (n=100)

Domain	Key Finding	Clinical Significance
Sex	74% Male	Occupational exposure, delayed care-seeking
Age at ulceration	54.22 ± 8.09 yrs	Peak productive age – high socioeconomic impact
Family history of DM	61%	Genetic clustering; early screening needed
Income source (daily wage)	54%	Financial barrier to drugs, footwear, follow-up
Unhygienic lifestyle	78%	Foot hygiene gap; undetected wounds
Habitual smoking/alcohol	49%	Accelerates PVD; impairs wound healing
Medication: Monotherapy only	69%	Insufficient for glycaemic control; driver of Grade 3-5
First consult: Hakeem/non-specialist	68%	Delayed evidence-based wound care initiation
Irregular follow-up	48%	Undetected glycaemic deterioration and neuropathy
Comorbidity burden	76%	Limits drug choices; impairs healing capacity
Psychological burden (family fear)	77%	Suppresses care-seeking; reduces adherence
Mean BMI	23.99 ± 4.80	Near Asian overweight threshold; elevated plantar pressure
Mean ABI	0.571 ± 0.201	Moderate PVD; 22% critical PAD (<0.4)
Mean 10g MFT	2.484 ± 2.251 sites	94% high-risk neuropathy; mode = 0 sensation
Mean HbA1c	9.581 ± 1.760%	Severely uncontrolled; 62% >8% (untreated level)

Wagner Grade 2-3	65%	Advanced deep ulcers; majority of clinical burden
Wagner Grade 4-5 (gangrene)	22%	Critical; amputation risk; preventable with early care

The cumulative risk profile Table 5, of the 100 DFU patients is the complete version of Table 4, providing a summary for the discussion and recommendations below.

IV. DISCUSSION

The totality of the analyses in this paper illustrates the interaction of a number of, overlapping and self-augmenting, risk factors to produce the burden of DFU at GIMS Khairpur. It's much more than one factor. As such the story of DFU in this population is the story of how they interact such that this population is at risk because socioeconomic vulnerabilities interact with behavioural risk factors, behavioural risk factors interact with under- or mal-mediation, under- or mal-mediation interact with chronic hyperglycemia, and chronic hyperglycemia interacts with peripheral artery and nerve dysfunction to make a minor wound on the foot a gangrenous infection. The tables and table-crosses (cross-tabulation) in this paper are the summary of this process for the first time in DFU patients from rural Sindh.

HbA1c-Medication Interactions: The Pharmacological Gap

Table 1 is the essence of this paper. It is not the HbA1c values (highest in all groups) which are important but the changing gradients within medication groups. In the non-adherent group 87.9% had HbA1c >8%. Among patients with monotherapy 97.8% had HbA1c greater than 7%. Of the combination group, 94.1% had HbA1c above 7% but the number of patients above 8% was less (52.9% vs. 60.0% with monotherapy). Only the three patients receiving combined treatment (the only group to receive Glucophage and insulin plus other medications to treat PDN and PVD) had lower HbA1c (6.7-7%) - the only group to approach near-target haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c).

There is an explanation for the gradient There is a strong and consistent maximum efficacy for monotherapy with the recommended first line drug (Glucophage) for this disease. In the progression of DMT2, with a loss of beta-cell function, monotherapy with metformin maintains the HbA1c below 7% in the vast majority of patients without additional drugs. In the current study 97.8% of patients who were on monotherapy had HbA1c values above the treatment target: this demonstrates that maximum efficacy - and by far - has been achieved with monotherapy in the majority of the DMT2 patients. They needed to have had additional drug therapy many years ago. The consequent lack of drug therapy is not a medical problem; it is a logical consequence of a system whereby the cost of insulin, fear of injections and no regular HbA1c measurement to drive escalation of insulin dose result in patients remaining on inappropriate therapy until it has become inappropriate therapy. The three patients on combination therapy with an HbA1c approaching normal show that it is not impossible to normalise their blood glucose: it is blocked. A dedicated intervention program that offers subsidised combination therapy to the 69% of patients on monotherapy, three monthly checks of HbA1c to prompt insulin dose escalation would (in UKPDS terms) lead to a 37% reduction in microvascular complications per 1% reduction in HbA1c.7 In these patients with a mean HbA1c of 9.58 (as against a target of 7), the theoretical benefit is enormous and the cost marginal.

Age Life style Income Triangle of Vulnerability

Table 3 shows the relative analysis of age, lifestyle and income highlights a particular vulnerability triangle in the at-risk DFU sub-class in the given study, middle age (45-65 years), active but unhygienic lifestyle and daily-wage income. It is no accident. Most Khairpur's daily-wage earners in agriculture and construction industries are active

(standing and walking) and work in an "unhygienic" environment (no fresh drinking water at the workplaces, barefoot and/or poorly fitting shoe culture, long hours in contact with dirt and dust). So the active but unhygienic combination: active so sufficient foot trauma and cuts, but unhygienic so those minor trauma possible to get infected.

That the age range affected by DFU is older in the lazy-and-unhygienic group (50-70 years, 45-65 years in the active groups) suggests another peak mechanism, as equally prominent as the first. In lazy-and-unhygienic group, older, chronic, neuropathic patients develop callus ulcers from repeated load on plantar surfaces with absent sensation, which are different from blunt trauma, and (until they resolve) produce the deeper ulcers because they go unnoticed for months due to absent sensation. The breakdown by wound type of injury in lifestyle groups (in physical wounds in the active groups vs callus/occlusion of skin in sedentary groups) reflect this.

The policy triangle suggests DFU prevention is not a "one size fits all". Active working class patients need workplace foot care: subsidised footwear (through typical employer- or government-based schemes), access to foot hygiene in the work-site and education regarding foot care for minor foot injuries (such as going to a foot wound clinic early). Immobile older patients need regular check ups (even without symptoms), and occasional callus removal to slow the painless progression from callus to severe ulcer. Both women need improved glucose control but behavioural compliance of foot care needs to be congruent with their lifestyle factors.

ABI-MFT-Wagner Cascade: seeing the progression

The most important result of the cumulative analysis is presented in Table 4: the worsening of ABI and 10g MFT with increasing Wagner grade. The step-wise profile change from Grade 0-1 (relatively "normal" function of peripheral nerve and blood vessels) to Grade 2-3 (moderate PVD and severe neuropathy) to Grade 4-5 (critical PAD and no foot function) is not simply a statistical phenomenon; it is the clinical fingerprint of type

2 diabetic hyperglycemia progressively taking away the ability for peripheral sensory and vascular functions.

The most telling data point in this table is the Grade 4-5 profile in the table: ABI < 0.4 (a Doppler "toothbrush sound" indicating near-total occlusion of arterial flow), and 0 positive monofilament sites (absent protective sensation in the foot). It's the combination of critical ischaemia and loss of sensation (a neuroischaemic foot) universally recognised as the highest risk and most difficult DFU phenotype.⁹ It's the foot with no blood to grow into a wound and no pain to motivate medical attention and care; the likely outcome of any wound is amputation. While the high percentage (22%) of Grade 4-5 in this table (22 patients in this category) is not inevitable but the outcome of a decade of drug/health systems failure.

This table is the justification for a risk-based approach to DFU care in Khairpur. When Doppler ABI is <0.4 referral for surgery is required; dressings and antibiotics are ineffective. Patients with an ABI 0.4-0.69 and monofilament scores of less than 6 need intensive wound care (offloading); offloading, wound care and debridement, plus immediate HbA1c optimisation. Patients with ABI 0.7-0.9, MFT scores less than 8 are in the "preventative zone"; when medication can be corrected and foot care education can prevent the shift into the majority of Grade 2-3 patients. Had this assessment for all diabetic OPD included an ABI and a 10g Monofilament test, this grouping could be based on a life-long risk assessment rather than point in time of injury.

The Big Picture: Four PAPERS worth of lessons

The cumulative risk profile in the four papers is shown in table 5. It provides an impression of a group of people for whom DFU is not caused by the occasional epic failures, but the sustained failures in all areas of care. None of these factors alone would be expected to create a Grade 4-5 DFU, but the co-existence of the many of the factors creates a milieu where Grade 4-5 DFU is almost inevitable for many.

The maths of compounding: a daily wage-earning 54-year-old male patient with a family history of diabetes, engaged in active (albeit poor hygiene) labour, smoker is at risk. Add 69% only one drug and 48% no regular care, the biochemical milieu goes downhill - HbA1c, neuropathy and blood flow deteriorate. Add the mean ABI (ankle-brachial index) of 0.571 and 94% high-risk neuropathy, the risk of deep ulcers with minimal trauma on the foot is high. The 25% visits to Hakeem put off the start of effective treatment for weeks to months, with worsening ulceration. Perceived stigma and burden (77%) minimises the need for care. The result, 55% of this population with grade 3-5 ulceration is the inevitable consequence of this "multiplication of failure". This overarching approach has clear benefit for guidance on intervention strategies. Better medication or better follow up with community-based foot hygiene education or better follow up, will improve the overall rate by a small degree but it will not achieve the goal. A package of interventions, addressing multiple domains, is needed, which includes simultaneous focus on increasing medication, providing follow up, providing foot health promotion in the community, referring for Hakeem (see above), providing psychological support and counselling to the patient, annual measurement of the ABG and monofilament. This is what the International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) Guidelines 2019 and the ADA considers to be the minimal standard of care for best DFU prevention - not a goal for care, but a standard of care.

V. Policy Recommendations

The recommendations of the series are: (1) Mandatory recording of HbA1c in all diabetes OPD consultations with documentation of escalation to double therapy in cases with HbA1c levels greater than 7%; (2) Supply of insulin and double therapy from GIMS and District hospitals to subsidise the escalation of treatment in DM; (3) Addition of Ankle Brachial Index (ABI) and 10g Monofilament in all diabetes OPD consultations, with annual documentation; (4) Education of Hakeems about DFU to enable red-flag detection and referral (to include Hakeems in the

streamlined care process without taking over their ethical and cultural space in the community); (5) Community education about diabetes foot care among daily wage earners, including factory workers and Agricultural Extension Committees; (6) Psychosocial support and peer counselling as an integral part of DFU clinics to address the 77% amputation-related morbidity rate; (7) Recall systems for DFU patients with irregular follow-up through simple texting services that can be done on even feature phones; and (8)

VI. CONCLUSION

The data set of this meta-comparative can be used to refrain from pointing to single variables as the "burden of Khairpur, Sindh on the DFU burden of the world". None is the most "risky"; rather upstream risk variables, across "the whole of care" - from family history and daily/weeks-labour-wage income and beyond, to pharmacological failure (medication inadequacy of monotherapy use and Hakeem visit) - and yet, the near universal presence of neurological insults and exclusive moderate-to-severe vascular insults, result in 22% of a consecutive 100 patients presenting with using Grade 4-5 gangrenous ulcers.

The HbA1c x medication cross-table confirms the single most manipulator upstream variable of ulcer severity is pharmaceutical failure; the typical presentation of most of the monotherapy patients is HbA1c well above the 6% therapeutic target (and thus high Wagner grades). The mediation models of ABI_MFT-Wagner confirm that the vascular and neurological insults co-evolve with ulcers, in a stage-wise, physiologically correlated manner. The interaction of age-lifestyle-income confirms the most burdened age-lifestyle-income group for prevention - middle age daily wagers active but unhygienic - as middle-aged active but unhygienic daily wage earners.

The study's findings and recommendations to escalate medication based on HbA1c level; test ABI and monofilament; introduce Hakeem care; support the mental health of patients and community education for foot care in the Khairpur district - are affordable, evidence, and practice-based steps to minimise the prevalence, complications and amputations caused by DFU.

This needs support from GIMS, the Sindh Department of Health and community complicity throughout the district by health-care providers. Series limitations are the single-centre, one-time study design, which fuels no generalizability and causality inference. Future multi-centre, multi-time, prospective studies, with nerve conduction velocity studies, vascular studies and quality-of-life studies are recommended to strengthen the evidence base and research agenda highlighted in this first-of-a-kind series

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